

1 Tailored policies for perennial woody crops are crucial to advance 2 Sustainable Development

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43 Preface

44 Perennial woody crops, crucial to our diets and global economies, have the potential to play a
45 major role in achieving multiple Sustainable Development Goals pertaining to biodiversity
46 conservation, socioeconomic development, and climate change mitigation. However, this
47 potential is hindered by insufficient scientific and policy attention specific to perennial woody
48 crops, and by intensification of perennial crop cultivation in the form of monocropping with high
49 external inputs. In this Perspective we highlight the potential of properly managed and
50 incentivized perennial woody crops to support holistic sustainable development and urge
51 scientists and policymakers to develop an effective agenda to better harness their benefits.

52

53 **Keywords:** agricultural policy, agroecosystems, biodiversity conservation, common agricultural
54 policy, deforestation, sustainable agriculture, sustainable development goals, tree crops.

55

56 Most current agricultural models prioritize immediate economic profitability and increased
57 productivity at the expense of long-term sustainability¹. This has led to severe environmental
58 challenges such as habitat loss and fragmentation, water and air pollution, and soil degradation.
59 These issues are primary drivers of the ongoing biodiversity crisis² and have major impacts on
60 human health³. Biodiversity decline caused by unsustainable agriculture hampers nature's
61 contribution to people⁴, increases farmers' dependence on agrochemicals, and threatens food
62 security worldwide⁵. Therefore, finding solutions to minimize the adverse ecological impacts
63 derived from agriculture is key to reducing biodiversity loss^{6,7}, mitigating climate change and
64 adapting to its adverse effects⁸, ensuring food sovereignty⁹, and safeguarding the long-term
65 viability of agriculture⁵. Among the environmental targets set at the recent United Nations
66 Biodiversity Conference (COP 15) of the Convention of Biodiversity (CBD) in Kunming-Montreal
67 2022, eight are closely related to the management of agricultural landscapes, including target
68 10 for sustainable use of agricultural lands and target 18 for identifying and removing harmful
69 agricultural subsidies (<https://www.cbd.int/gbf/>). Addressing these issues is a multifaceted,
70 high-priority challenge at the interface of ecology and economics, and interfacing with social
71 issues such as human rights, equity (including access to land), and the fair distribution of wealth.

72 Cropping system design and management will play a key role in reaching post-2020 global
73 biodiversity targets^{10,11}. Perennial woody crops (hereafter also referred to as 'perennial crops'
74 for brevity) have great potential in the progress towards achieving Sustainable Development
75 Goals (SDGs) by reconciling agricultural production and biodiversity conservation. Although
76 agriculture has been a key driver of recent and ongoing land-use change, and perennial woody
77 crops have contributed to these changes (e.g., tropical deforestation¹²⁻¹⁴), some perennial
78 crops, if managed under sustainable principles, can be amenable to biodiversity conservation.
79 Furthermore, perennial cropping systems tend to be less mechanized and often require
80 significant human labor, offering the opportunity to reduce unemployment and support rural
81 livelihoods^{15,16}, especially in developing countries where many of these crops are grown.
82 Unfortunately, these potential benefits are often undermined by low wages, seasonal labor,
83 worker exploitation, and immigration¹⁶, problems that are exacerbated as perennial crop
84 production is intensified. This intensification partly reflects a lack of recognition of the ecological
85 and social significance of perennial crops, and a lack of incentives to promote sustainable
86 practices. Most agricultural policies aimed at improving environmental and economic
87 sustainability emphasize annual crop management (arable land), with very few specifically

88 targeting perennial crops¹⁷. A focus on annual crops is clearly important for improving
89 agricultural sustainability, and associated actions, such as Agri-environmental Schemes^{18,19} are
90 proving successful overall (albeit with scope for improvement²⁰). However, we argue that
91 leveraging the potential of perennial crops to contribute to SDGs for environmental and
92 economic sustainability requires more research, legislative support, and the implementation of
93 tailored policies^{21,22}.

94 In this Perspective we aim to highlight the unexploited potential of properly managed and
95 incentivized perennial woody crops to contribute to SDGs. In doing so, we do not aim to diminish
96 the importance of annual crops or to compare the two cropping systems. Rather, we emphasize
97 that annual and perennial crop systems each have particular risks and advantages that require
98 different management approaches (Supplementary Table 1). Although intensification affects
99 both systems and typically diminishes their contribution to SDGs, annual crops have on average
100 a lower ecological value even when properly managed due to their simpler structural complexity
101 and short-term dynamics^{23–25}. Perennial crops require a longer-term commitment from growers,
102 which make them less flexible and hence more vulnerable to climate change and novel pests
103 and diseases. Yet, perennial crops managed under agroecological principles with higher reliance
104 on ecological processes ('ecological intensification'²⁶) have substantial potential to contribute to
105 key SDGs. This results especially from their greater structural complexity, temporal stability, and
106 strategic presence in biodiversity-rich and socio-economically developing regions¹⁰. We argue
107 that new, complementary agricultural policies should aim to maximize the contribution of
108 perennial woody crops to SDGs, and counter the current trend toward unsustainable farming in
109 these systems.

110

111 **Relevance of perennial crops for the SDGs**

112 Perennial woody crops typically include plantations of fruit trees (e.g. citrus), nut trees (cashews,
113 walnuts, or almonds), berry plantations (blueberries), stimulants (coffee, cocoa, tea), vine crops,
114 and palm and olive tree plantations, among others. Although not woody, we include bananas
115 and plantains in this discussion as they are ecologically and socio-economically important tree-
116 like perennial crops. Perennial crops cover ca. 183 M ha worldwide, many of which overlap with
117 key biodiversity hotspots²⁷. For instance, coffee is extensively grown in tropical areas of
118 Mesoamerica, olive trees in the Mediterranean Basin hotspot, cocoa in the Guinean Forests of
119 West Africa, and oil palm in Sundaland (Fig. 1 and Supplementary Table 2).

120 As with any other cropping system, perennial woody crops inherently conflict with the
121 conservation of the natural habitats they replace. However, some of their characteristics can
122 make them compatible with biodiversity conservation. Their heterogeneous and often forest-
123 like structure, encompassing many vegetation layers, offers a wide range of micro- and
124 macrohabitats that can support high diversity, including native plant species in the herbaceous
125 cover (e.g., vineyards, olive or apple groves), overhead shade trees (e.g., cocoa, or coffee), and
126 mixed species associations^{29–32}. Consequently, a high number of vertebrate and invertebrate
127 taxa can coexist in these agroecosystems^{33–36}. In addition to the inherent structural
128 heterogeneity, perennial crops occupy the land over multiple years without replanting, offering
129 relatively stable habitats within and across years. As a result, habitat and species diversity can
130 be more easily maintained in perennial crop systems compared to arable crops.

131 Many perennial woody crops have extensive root structures, provide abundant litter, and thus
132 can reduce soil erosion, increase soil fertility and soil health, minimize nutrient leaching, and

133 provide permanent habitats for many species^{37–39}, while being highly productive (i.e., ca. 1
134 billion metric tons a year worldwide, FAOstats, 2021). Furthermore, woody tree-like perennial
135 crops can help reduce greenhouse gases through above and belowground carbon
136 sequestration^{39–41}. Perennial crop systems can also act as a permeable matrix through which
137 wildlife can travel between forest patches, enhancing connectivity and contributing to the
138 maintenance of fragmented forest populations as metapopulations⁴². As such, they can buffer
139 protected areas and other natural and semi-natural habitats within intensively managed
140 agricultural landscapes⁴³.

141 Perennial crops can thus, when correctly managed, support a wide range of plant and animal
142 species alongside the crop, playing a key role in reconciling biodiversity conservation with the
143 needs of people – and in some cases maximizing nature’s contribution to people (Fig. 2 and
144 Supplementary Figure 1). Nevertheless, leveraging these opportunities requires greater
145 representation in the scientific literature (Fig. 3), and in agricultural policies.

146 Most potential gains discussed here pertain to diversified woody or tree-like perennial crops
147 because of their high biomass and complex structure. However, it is worth noting that
148 herbaceous perennial crops, such as alfalfa, also cover extensive areas and are also highly
149 relevant for biodiversity and soil health⁴⁴. Given the substantial advantages of perennial
150 herbaceous crops over their annual counterparts^{23,45,46}, significant effort is underway to develop
151 and cultivate perennial varieties of key herbaceous species (e.g., grains)^{25,47}. Developing new
152 and improved crop varieties, while preserving the genetic diversity of crops, could be crucial,
153 particularly in marginal landscapes, resource-constrained settings, and in regions facing
154 increased drought from climate change^{45,46}.

155

156 **Legislation gaps harm conservation efforts**

157 With a few exceptions (see ASEAN 2022 Regional Guidelines for sustainable palm oil
158 production), perennial cropping systems have received limited attention within the global
159 agricultural policy framework. For example, there is no explicit mention of perennial crops in the
160 latest agricultural policy monitoring and evaluation report conducted by the Organization for
161 Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), which encompasses agricultural legislation
162 from 54 countries worldwide¹⁷. This is surprising given the overarching theme of this report, i.e.,
163 "Reforming Agricultural Policies for Climate Change Mitigation". Another example is the
164 European Union (EU), known for its wide-ranging agricultural policies and a substantial budget
165 to implement them (e.g., €387 billion for the period 2023-2027). In the EU, perennial crops have
166 historically been considered ‘green’ by definition, and it is only in the most recent reform of the
167 Common Agricultural Policy (CAP 2023-2027) that guidelines specific to them have been
168 introduced, such as the conservation of living or inert ground cover. Although these guidelines
169 represent a step forward, they fall short of fully realizing the potential of perennial crops for
170 conserving agrobiodiversity and promoting sustainability. Furthermore, long-term
171 unsustainable incentives persist, such as the promotion of inefficient irrigation systems that
172 deplete groundwater in semiarid rainfed Mediterranean crops, or the exemption of perennial
173 crops from some environmental requirements. For instance, according to EU-CAP, establishing
174 seminatural areas of non-production for nature (formerly known as 'set-aside', now a
175 component of ‘Good agricultural and environmental conditions’ or GAEC) is a requirement that
176 only applies to arable crops, with perennial crops and grasslands essentially exempt. Moreover,
177 payments for specific sectors – such as fruit trees, olives, and wine – are not attached to

178 environmental standards, meaning that the opportunity is missed to secure their environmental
179 value. More worryingly, it is precisely in perennial crops that, in Europe, contamination by the
180 so-called 'Candidates for substitution' (that is, pesticides listed as hazardous to humans) has
181 seen a steep rise in recent years, reaching extremely high levels in fruits such as cherries, apples,
182 pears, peaches and kiwi (PAN 2022, <https://www.pan-europe.info/>).

183 Specific environmental legislation regarding the long-term sustainability of perennial crop
184 landscapes is virtually absent globally¹⁷. This limited focus and presence of proactive measures
185 have been a contributor to the ongoing rapid trend towards deforestation¹²⁻¹⁴, and extreme
186 intensification of many perennial crops worldwide, especially in tropical areas. For instance, Jha
187 et al. (2014) found that the area of traditional shaded coffee decreased from 43% to 24% in 19
188 countries between 1996 and 2010, resulting in high biodiversity loss⁴⁸. This general trend, also
189 generalizable to other perennial crops and areas, poses an important threat to biodiversity and
190 sustainability across millions of hectares worldwide⁴⁹ (Fig. 4).

191 Some of the most frequent and environmentally damaging practices within perennial crops
192 currently include: (i) loss of forest- or savannah-like structure as traditional low-density orchards
193 are replaced by hyper-dense planting lines (i.e., hedge-like plantations)^{50,51}; (ii) loss of soil and
194 decline in soil quality through frequent tillage and, especially, the use of pre- and post-
195 emergence herbicides that leave bare soils by persistently removing herbaceous cover⁵²; (iii)
196 loss of crop diversity and genetic/varieties diversity^{53,54}; and iv) loss of landscape complexity
197 through the removal of field margins and patches of semi-natural vegetation and reduction of
198 native flora in agroecosystems⁶. These negative practices can often co-occur, as in super-
199 intensive olive, apple, or even coffee/cacao farming systems, turning traditional (often
200 smallholder) forest-like agroecosystems into high-input, hyperdense monocultures (Fig. 5, and
201 Supplementary Table 3).

202 Besides the conservation threats arising from unsustainable practices, there are also crucial
203 socio-economic consequences to consider. Current models for perennial crop cultivation, which
204 rely heavily on rapid and extensive automation and mechanization, contribute to rural
205 unemployment, a major political challenge worldwide⁵⁵. Moreover, the prevalence of corporate
206 farming — large-scale monocultures owned by major companies — fosters a decline in
207 community engagement and leads to income reduction for millions of people worldwide⁷. Since
208 ensuring a decent job for all is one of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG-8), avoiding
209 extreme levels of mechanization and promoting fair and stable labor for people appears to offer
210 a viable approach to balancing employment and profit, especially when striving to ensure an
211 equitable redistribution of profits among stakeholders.

212 In light of the prevailing tendency towards less sustainable agricultural practices, it is timely to
213 stress the need for national and international agricultural policies that strategically allocate
214 targeted and tailored incentives aimed at fostering socially responsible and sustainable
215 perennial crop cultivation. Measures in this direction (e.g., the minimum social and labor
216 standards to receive subsidies implemented in the last CAP within the European Union) have
217 the potential to safeguard the long-term sustainability and ecological value of these agricultural
218 systems, while ensuring equitable incomes for farm households and laborers, and thus
219 supporting the progress of other SDGs, such as providing decent jobs and economic
220 development.

221

222 **Policies for perennial crop sustainability**

223 Solutions offering a favorable balance between production and sustainability exist, but
224 agricultural policies are still inadequate in encouraging farmers to adopt them.

225 The viability of sustainable agricultural practices largely depends on economic benefits for
226 farmers and wider society^{56,57}. Payment of incentives for ecosystem service provision has been
227 highly effective at promoting sustainable practices in some contexts^{7,58}. Nevertheless, the
228 complex nature of agroecosystems, influenced by diverse socio-political circumstances, means
229 that there is no one-size-fits-all solution applicable to all ecological and socio-economic contexts.
230 Therefore, we share our vision about the status and threats to key perennial crops worldwide
231 (Fig. 5 and Supplementary Table 3), and propose the incentivization of specific practices to
232 promote more sustainable agriculture in key agroecosystems (Fig. 6 and Supplementary Table
233 4), such as oil palm, cocoa, coffee, olive, grapevine, banana, citrus and apple (extended in
234 Supplementary Notes 1 to 8), to increase their sustainability and support the progress towards
235 SDGs⁵⁹.

236 We identify three priorities. Firstly, most perennial woody crops will benefit from within-field
237 and landscape-level management practices that foster biodiversity (i.e., ‘ecological
238 intensification’)²⁶, and those good practices often require both regulation and economic
239 incentives⁵⁶. Secondly, for some perennial crops grown in tropical biodiversity hotspots (e.g.
240 cocoa, coffee, or oil palm), there is a need for stricter regional land use planning together with
241 international trade regulation efforts to adjust offer and demand⁶⁰. Such regulations should
242 target the whole food chain and are necessary to ensure deforestation is halted and reversed.
243 Finally, transitioning towards agricultural sustainability demands a holistic and multidimensional
244 approach. This involves integrating a variety of tools across the entire food chain into policy
245 design, creating targeted campaigns for technology adoption, and providing comprehensive
246 support to farmers through training, extension programs, financial aid, fair prices (i.e., living
247 income reference price), and incentives. Addressing market access, certification standards,
248 consumer awareness, and fostering participatory approaches are equally crucial. A combination
249 of incentives, such as subsidies for biodiversity-friendly farming practices, payments for
250 ecosystem services, or results-based payments, can significantly enhance conservation
251 outcomes. Additionally, measures such as tax reductions, insurance support for farmers willing
252 to sacrifice some yield in favor of more sustainable practices, assistance with certification
253 processes, promotion of sustainable products, support for implementing adaptive measures
254 against climate change risks, and land stewardship programs can further reinforce these efforts.

255

256 **Intertwined complexities and a way forward**

257 Legislating agriculture is a complex challenge since there are multiple trade-offs and
258 interconnections between ecological, economic, and social components. In this context,
259 solutions are not absolute and universal but need to be implemented progressively and revised
260 to avoid undesired outcomes. In particular, much work remains to be done to understand the
261 interplay between various socio-economic and ecological dimensions in different key
262 agroecosystems, particularly perennial crops, and how to maximize benefits in some
263 components (e.g., farmer profitability or rural development) without compromising others (e.g.,
264 biodiversity conservation)⁵⁶.

265 The first key aspect is that a large fraction of biodiversity-friendly measures relates to promoting
266 smallholders. However, it is crucial to recognize that smallholders often lack the capacity to
267 implement efficient and sustainable practices due to limited resources, while some larger

268 producers could transition more easily towards sustainable farming. Therefore, it is important
269 to consider that the type and extent of exploitation are affected by various economic, social,
270 and environmental factors affecting farmer's decisions. Accordingly, support should be tailored
271 to farmers' capacities and needs, to ensure that larger producers are incentivized to pursue
272 agroecological efforts, while vulnerable farmers receive sufficient help to adopt sustainable
273 practices without compromising their livelihoods⁶¹. Similarly, regulations can prove ineffective
274 if we do not tackle problems such as the unfair distribution of the income generated by perennial
275 crops across the food chain; decentralizing food chains could help in this context⁵⁶. Regulating
276 crop production cannot be done without integrating the social, economic, and ecological
277 dimensions, and their interconnections and ramifications. Pressing global issues such as food
278 waste, climate change, food security challenges, and biodiversity loss depend heavily on the
279 actions we suggest here.

280 Second, we need to understand how potential solutions at small scales can work when
281 implemented at larger scales, as we still have poor knowledge about the feedback effects
282 (positive or negative) of large-scale expansion of sustainable practices⁶². For example, imposing
283 a fast transition towards organic agriculture in a generalized manner, without properly
284 facilitating the transition, can have positive results for biodiversity, but bring problematic
285 consequences for food production and food security if yields decrease significantly (e.g. due to
286 elevated pest damage) and products become unavailable or unaffordable for part of the
287 population⁶³. In some cases, certifications or labels (e.g., organic or fair-trade for coffee or
288 cocoa) have been implemented successfully to distinguish specific products in the market,
289 encouraging more sustainable management in these systems. This assumes that a segment of
290 the public is willing to pay more for certified products. However, predicting market behavior
291 becomes challenging as the proportion of production achieving certification increases, and
292 certification might only work if certified products are relatively scarce. Hence, while we support
293 the promotion of certified products through economic incentives, international customs duties,
294 and national tax differentials to alleviate the certification costs incurred by farmers, this
295 recommendation should be revisited in the midterm once higher market quotas for certified
296 products are reached.

297 Third, some of the key problems in agriculture are inherent to the current market system and
298 predominant consumption model. Therefore, a deep transformation in the way people purchase
299 and consume agricultural goods and products could be needed to change these dynamics. For
300 instance, many tree crops yield non-essential products from a nutritional standpoint that are
301 consumed far from the production areas, which is often regarded as less sustainable compared
302 to using local products. Hence, as a society, we should reflect on the biodiversity impacts of
303 consumption of non-local and non-essential products, and on which crops we would like to
304 prioritize to promote healthy and nutritious diets; for example, crops with high protein content.

305 Reflecting on these complexities, we argue that the following three key are crucial to achieving
306 SDGs. Firstly, international trade needs international agreements focusing on the entire supply
307 chain. Countries and companies that import products from producing areas (often located in
308 developing countries in Latin America, Africa and Asia) should also take responsibility for the
309 socio-economic and ecological impacts of these transactions (e.g., waive customs duties or avoid
310 externalization of environmental damage)⁶⁰. Working on international agreements could have a
311 positive impact on the way we produce food and on people's livelihoods worldwide. Special care
312 must be taken not to shift the burden of environmental protection onto smallholder farmers,
313 who typically have lower incomes and are more vulnerable to both environmental stresses and

314 the economic and social impacts of agricultural policies. Instead, they should be supported and
315 incentivized to adopt sustainable practices while also ensuring they receive a fair income. For
316 example, rising temperatures and erratic rainfall patterns driven by climate change are
317 increasingly affecting the production and profitability of some perennial crops such as cocoa,
318 coffee, and citrus. This is particularly critical for smallholder farmers whose livelihoods are
319 closely linked to these crops⁶⁴. Addressing the challenges posed by climate change for these
320 perennial crops requires ingenuity from smallholder farmers and support to implement adaptive
321 measures including shade-planting, establishment of cover vegetation to protect the soil
322 (including marketable crops), or rainwater harvesting and provision of irrigation^{65,66}. Smallholder
323 farmers, especially those in dryland farming systems, are also confronted with non-climatic
324 stressors (e.g., limited access to markets and inadequate agricultural equipment) that are often
325 exacerbated by existing inequalities in relation to access to land and other productive capital
326 resources⁶⁷. These challenges drive smallholders' vulnerability to climatic and non-climatic
327 threats including food insecurity. Therefore, there is an urgent need for holistic policy
328 interventions that could empower smallholders to adopt new, efficient, and sustainable
329 practices where possible. Additionally, larger commercial growers can learn from smallholders
330 (e.g., about the use of different parts of the plants). The exchange of knowledge and practices
331 should be mutual, ensuring that different types of farmers benefit both environmentally and
332 economically. Secondly, each agricultural system has its particular problems and needs, and one
333 policy will not fit them all. While some regions should focus on the protection and conservation
334 of natural areas (e.g., palm oil production) using regulatory policies and land-use planning,
335 others should concentrate on restoring already degraded lands, semi-natural habitats in
336 exploitation, and the surrounding landscape through incentives (e.g., olive farms, vineyards, or
337 apple orchards). Thirdly, the multiple socio-political feedbacks and interactions in place imply
338 that policies cannot work in isolation from society and local communities. Rather, a socio-
339 cultural and economic context that facilitates the evolution and development of green and
340 equitable policies should be fostered. There is a need to work bottom-up with local communities
341 to incentivize and encourage local sustainable crops and ensure the uptake of such policies by
342 local communities, instead of enforcing market needs upon them.

343 In conclusion, perennial crops can play a crucial role in harmonizing agriculture and the
344 achievement of the SDGs if correctly managed. However, their significance warrants increased
345 attention in scientific research and agricultural policies. Neglecting the value of perennial crops
346 can lead to increased unsustainability, accelerating a myriad of environmental and social issues,
347 that are compounded by climate change. To secure the future of agriculture and biodiversity,
348 and progress towards the achievement of the SDGs, governments should consider legislative
349 support and tailored policies for perennial woody crops. A variety of actions proposed here could
350 promote sustainable practices in perennial crop cultivation globally, reducing biodiversity loss,
351 supporting livelihoods and rural development, addressing climate change concerns and building
352 resilience of farmers especially smallholders, and enhancing food security in the years ahead.
353 The ultimate goal of this article is to bring attention to this issue, stimulate debate involving as
354 many actors as possible, and motivate policymakers and scientists to place this important matter
355 on their agenda.

356

357 **Additional information**

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359

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377

378 Author contributions

379 C.M.-N. conceptualized the study, coordinated the team, and wrote the first draft of the
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386 Competing interests

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- 552
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554 **Fig. 1: Overlap between the main perennial woody crops and hotspots of biodiversity.**
555 Orange shading indicates areas where any of the following perennial crops are grown: oil palm,
556 bananas and plantains, cacao, coffee, coconut, olives, grapevine, cashew nuts, mangoes,
557 apple, orange²⁸. Green shading indicates the main biodiversity hotspots according to Myers et
558 al., 2000 (revised version, 2016)²⁷.

559

560 **Fig. 2: The importance of perennial woody crops worldwide.** A) World map showing six of the
561 most important perennial crops in terms of area coverage and socio-economic impact. The
562 world map and plant icons were modified from <https://freesvg.org>. B) Main ecosystem services
563 provided by perennial crops worldwide. C) Area covered in the year 2021 by each crop (the
564 production area of bananas, including plantains and cooking bananas, reaches 12 M ha), and
565 potential for biodiversity conservation and ecosystem services provision by key perennial crops
566 worldwide. Although not woody, we include bananas as they are ecologically and socio-
567 economically important tree-like perennial crops. See Supplementary Figure 1 for a fully
568 referenced version.

569

570 **Fig. 3: Scientific attention received by perennial woody crops and annual crops.** The figure
571 illustrates the total number of publications indexed in the Web of Science (grey) and the
572 subset of publications within the field of Environmental Sciences (blue) that are related to
573 specific keywords like 'annual crop' or 'wheat'. The search was done in June 2024. Note that
574 high scientific attention does not necessarily imply that effective measures are properly
575 deployed.

576

577 **Fig. 4: Effects of agricultural practices in perennial crops along the sustainability gradient.**
578 Environmental and socio-economic negative effects driven by unsustainable production in
579 perennial crops, showcased by extremes of sustainability in three key perennial crops
580 worldwide (coffee, olive, and grapevine). Coffee pictures courtesy of Jacques Avelino. Pictures
581 of olive farms courtesy of Pedro J. Rey. Pictures of grapevines courtesy of Sophie Chamont
582 (top) and Sylvie Richart Cervera (bottom).

583

584 **Fig. 5: Main threats to the sustainability of key perennial crops worldwide.** Principal risks facing
585 specific perennial woody crops were highlighted by experts on each crop. 'Environmentally less
586 sustainable practices' refer to actions under the control of farmers, whereas 'Economically less
587 sustainable practices' and broader 'Threats to sustainable production' require the involvement
588 of multiple stakeholders, including scientists, society, and politicians. This list is not exhaustive;
589 only the priority threats are highlighted for each crop and other secondary threats may also
590 apply. *Although bananas are not woody, they are included due to their ecological and socio-
591 economic importance as tree-like perennial crops.

592

593 **Fig. 6: Agricultural practices and farming models that could be incentivized by new agricultural**
594 **policies.** These actions could help to increase the ecological and socio-economic long-term
595 sustainability of key perennial crops worldwide. The proposed solutions are based on expert
596 knowledge and scientific literature (see Supplementenyst for an extended commentary on each
597 one, with supporting citations). 'Agricultural practices to incentivize' are actions under the

598 control of farmers, whereas 'Goals and areas of priority policy investment' require the
599 involvement of multiple stakeholders including scientists, civil society, and politicians. 'SDGs
600 enhanced' indicates the environmental and socio-economic realms that each action would
601 improve. SDGs: 1 (no poverty), 6 (clean water and sanitation), 8 (decent work and economic
602 growth), 10 (reduced inequality), 12 (responsible production and consumption), 13 (climate),
603 and 15 (life on land). * Although not woody, we include bananas and plantain as ecologically and
604 socio-economically important tree-like perennial crops. Other details are analogous to those in
605 Fig. 5.